

D7.1 Project Website

www.teamup2restore.eu

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 7.1 explains the guiding principles, steps and tools implemented to build an effective and user-friendly website. It focuses on the process and the rationale behind developing the TEAM#UP website.

Deliverable	D7.1 Project Website
Work Package	7
Due of Deliverable	Month 4
Lead beneficiary of this deliverable	SERE, Society for Ecological Restoration, Chapter Europe
Version	V.1
Author(s) and Institution(s)	Andrea Troncoso, Boris Barov, SERE
Submission Date	14 October 2023
Reviewers	Ryan Campbell, HSA Lenka Sebelikova, USB

Dissemination level

PU	Public
----	--------

Table of contents

Summary	4
List of Acronyms	5
1. Introduction	6
2. TEAM#UP, an overview of the project	6
2.1. The objectives of TEAM#UP	
Table 1: Overview of TEAM#UP Work Packages	
3. Project Website	9
3.1 Sitemap	
3.2 Website pictures	

Summary

This document corresponds to Deliverable 7.1, *D7.1 Project Website*, the first deliverable assigned to the WP7, Communication & Dissemination, led by SERE, the Society for Ecological Restoration, Chapter Europe and USB, University of South Bohemia.

It presents the rationale for developing the website, which will be part of the TEAM#UP Communication Strategy. In this framework, the TEAM#UP website will be a crucial tool to reach out to different audiences and share the development and outcomes of the project, especially the Digital Open Education Resources, one of the principal axes.

Communicating the results of an EU-funded project via an effective website is relevant to its success. It allows to inform diverse target groups about the project's milestones and outcomes. It contributes to shed light on the impact of EU funding while building a stronger sense of the European community.

List of Acronyms relevant to this deliverable:

HSA	Anhalt University of Applied Sciences
SER	Society for Ecological Restoration, Chapter Europe
USB	University of South Bohemia
VET	Vocational Education and Training
OER	Open Educational Resources
ER	Ecological Restoration
EU	European Union

1. Introduction

TEAM#UP is an Erasmus+ funded project to share knowledge, tool training and resources for ecological restoration with different communities. It is a 4-year project from June 2023 to June 2027.

TEAM#UP's vision is to serve as a hub and become a reference point for mainstreaming restoration activities with Vocational Education and Training, VET, schools, universities and sector partners, facilitating the transition to a greener and climate-resilient society.

Communication and dissemination via an effective website along the project's timeline will contribute to reaching target audiences and sharing the dedicated resources designed, created and produced for VET in the field of ER.

2. TEAM#UP, an overview of the project

2.1. The objectives of TEAM#UP

TEAM#UP will contribute to promoting, through innovative educational schemes, the transition to greener and climate-resilient economies, as called for in the Green Deal. It underpins educational programs liaising with practitioners via green VET that includes a wide range of learnings, to name a few:

Digital tools (e.g., visualisation of demonstration sites with augmented/virtual reality); Standards, protocols and priority of actions; Restoration technologies and approaches; Monitoring techniques and approaches; Financial mechanisms; Stakeholder engagement and

Science-policy-industry interface. Our main goal is to mobilise extensive knowledge and skills in ecological ER to fill gaps in green VET. We want to counteract the ongoing biodiversity loss and habitat degradation to strengthen ecosystem functions and services in the face of climate change.

TEAM#UP has set up eight specific objectives, which its seven Work Packages will address.

Objective 1: Develop ecological restoration curricula for VETs targeting the pressing needs of future professionals across sectors to successfully implement European green strategies, engaging multiple actors from the public, private and non-profit sectors

Objective 2: Implement four specific curricula as OER in ecological restoration for VET

Objective 3: Use and advancement of demonstration sites to spur hands-on skills, responsibility and autonomy in VET on ER

Objective 4: Foster reciprocal exchange of needs, knowledge, skills, and competencies between secondary and tertiary education providers, scientists and practitioners at the regional and national level

Objective 5: Initiate international knowledge exchange and collaborative curricula development of students and teachers at nationally oriented VET providers

Objective 6: Showing the added value of ER as a business model and career opportunity

Objective 7: Communicate on the education of ER in the context of VET and transfer to other countries

Objective 8: Sustainability and long-term impact of TEAM#UP on education in ER

Table 1: Overview of TEAM#UP Work Packages

Work Package and leading institution	Work Package's main aim
WP1 Coordination and Monitoring, HSA	This work package will take care of the sustainability and long-term impact of TEAM#UP on education in ER and will support the fulfillment of all other objectives.
WP2 Cooperative module development, HSA	This work package will develop ecological restoration curricula for VETs to successfully implement European green strategies while engaging multiple actors from the public, private and non-profit sectors. It will also implement four specific curricula as OER in ecological restoration for VET.
WP3 Open Educational Resources Development, CIDA	This work package will support the use and advancement of demonstration sites to spur hands-on skills, responsibility and autonomy in VET on ER.
WP4 Pilot implementation and evaluation, NINA	This work package will Implement four specific curricula as OER in ecological restoration for VET.
WP5 Business models, funding and governance, UA	This work package will show the added value of ER as a business model and career opportunity.
WP6 National outreach and integration into further education, UA	This work package will foster the reciprocal exchange of needs, knowledge, skills, and competencies between secondary and tertiary education providers, scientists and practitioners at regional and national levels.

WP7 Dissemination, impact, and European exchange, USB	This work package will communicate the education of ER in the context of VET and transfer to other countries, supporting exchange and sustainability.
---	---

3. Project Website

TEAM#UP's website has been developed to showcase the project's process, results and leading activities to the public. The website has been built with the support of a web development company under the guiding principles of simplicity, user-friendliness, and minimalism. The company appointed to develop an appealing website is the experienced Pensoft Publishers. The company will be in charge of hosting the website for ten years.

The TEAM#UP website was created as an independent site, not as a microsite on the SERE website. This decision was made in order to maximise functionality, design characteristics, and impact of the project website as developed by a professional company rather than done 'in-house' by SERE. In this way, the webpage can be edited by the project team members, and the news and updates can be added regularly. There will, however, be a SERE webpage dedicated to TEAM#UP and linked to the project website. This fulfils all beneficiaries' requirements: creating a webpage linked to the project website.

The website was developed between September and October 2023, and it will allow SERE, USB and HSA to update content without advanced programming skills. It is user-friendly, and it features a clean, elegant and impactful front end. The web address of the website is www.TeamUp2Restore.eu

The planning of the website included regular online meetings with the developers, follow-ups via email, and systematic communication between SER, the project coordinator and the Consortium to gather

information to be featured in the website, feedback and fine-tuning with partners' needs and collecting relevant ideas to move forward.

Several concepts were considered in the final proposed design:

- the TEAM#UP website has to convey the project's spirit, resonating with restoration, teamwork, openness and innovation.
- the TEAM#UP website has to look fresh, modern and appealing.
- the TEAM#UP website must showcase the potential of VET
- the TEAM#UP website must be easy to navigate and not overloaded with information.
- the TEAM#UP website must have some elements in motion.

The website also presents the new TEAM#UP logo, which has been designed by the same company, considering the input from the Consortium. Two rounds of proposals and the discussion between partners led to this final decision:

- a) The logo shows collaborative work: the hands in the shape of a hashtag
- b) Conveys a sense of advancement: the arrow point of the U in the word UP
- c) Communicates a link to nature through its colours and the icons of leaves

In this sense, the website includes the logo and the colour palette deriving from this design. A brand manual is being prepared at the time of the submission of this deliverable. It will guide further updates in terms of design, among other guides.

The website will be launched on 13 October 2023.

3.1 Sitemap

TEAM#UP website has a dynamic homepage allowing easy navigation by scrolling. The user will immediately grasp the available content by scrolling down. As mentioned above, this site and the OER will be linked to the SER website, as planned in the proposal.

Building on exchanges with the whole Consortium, the following wireframe was considered for the website:

Social media icons				
About us	Open Educational Resources	News	Events	Contact us
Context and aim	Category 1	News		
What is ecological restoration?	Category 2	Press releases		
Workplan		Newsletter		
Deliverables		Multimedia		
Partners				
Advisory Board -AB-(this item is considered but will be added once the AB is active)				
Cookies				
Erasmus acknowledgement				
Social media icons				

The website contains several sections. The first briefly presents the project's objectives, as well as the project partners and advisory board. The drop-down menu in this first section contains relevant information about restoration. The second section of the website presents the Open Educational Resources. A section called News collects news, press releases and the latest information about events, and a webpage dedicated to the newsletter. The website, which will showcase progress along the project's timeline, also features a footer displaying social media icons to multiply visibility over diverse platforms.

Future deliverables and milestones are linked to integrating the Open Educational Resource (Digital Ecological Restoration Toolbox: DERTO) platform into the website. DERTO will be hosted by the Society for Ecological Restoration International's Restoration Resource Center and linked to the project website.

The following screenshots show different pages of the website in its current state, just being launched.

3.2 Website pictures

Workplan

TEAM#UP's main goal is to mobilize extensive knowledge and skills in the field of ecological restoration (ER) to fill gaps in green Vocational Education Training (VET).

For this, we have set up eight specific objectives, which will be addressed by its seven Work Packages.

Objectives

Objective 1

Develop ecological restoration curricula for VETs targeting pressing needs of future professionals across sectors to successfully implement European green strategies, engaging multiple actors from the public, private and non-profit sectors

Objective 2

Implement four specific curricula as OER in ecological restoration for VET

Objective 3

Use and advancement of demonstration sites to spur hands-on skills, responsibility and autonomy in VET on ecological restoration

Objective 4

Foster reciprocal exchange of needs, knowledge, skills, and competences between secondary and tertiary education providers, scientists and practitioners at regional and national level

TEAM#UP will contribute to promoting, through innovative educational schemes, the transition to greener and climate-resilient economies, as called for in the Green Deal.

TEAM#UP underpins with educational programs liaising with practitioners via green vocational education and training (VET) that includes a wide range of learnings, to name a few: Digital tools (e.g., visualization of demonstration sites with augmented/virtual reality); Standards, protocols and priority of actions; Restoration technologies and approaches; Monitoring techniques and approaches; Financial mechanisms; Stakeholder engagement and Science-policy-industry interface.

Our main goal is to mobilize extensive knowledge and skills in the field of ecological restoration to fill gaps in green VET. We want to counteract the ongoing biodiversity loss and habitat degradation in order to strengthen ecosystem functions and services in the face of climate change.

Workplan

TEAM#UP's main goal is to mobilize extensive knowledge and skills in the field of ecological restoration (ER) to fill gaps in green Vocational Education Training (VET).

For this, we have set up eight specific objectives, which will be addressed by its seven Work Packages.

Objectives

Objective 1

Develop ecological restoration curricula for VETs targeting pressing needs of future professionals across sectors to successfully implement European green strategies, engaging multiple actors from the public, private and non-profit sectors

Objective 2

Implement four specific curricula as OER in ecological restoration for VET

Objective 3

Use and advancement of demonstration sites to spur hands-on skills, responsibility and autonomy in VET on ecological restoration

Objective 4

Foster reciprocal exchange of needs, knowledge, skills, and competences between secondary and tertiary education providers, scientists and practitioners at regional and national level

